

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2017
RGN19/ RM 14 (PNM 121) PSYCHOLOGY IN NURSING-
TIME ALLOWED-1 ½ HRS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any marks

QUESTION ONE

- a. Mention any Two (2) components or characteristics of personality - 2 marks
- b. State One (1) similarity between the following;
- i. Oral stage and id - 2 marks
- ii. Oral stage and trust versus mistrust - 2 marks
- c. i. Define learning? - 2 marks
- ii. Mention any Three (3) theories of learning and the personalities behind them? - 6 marks
- d. Enumerate six (6) importance of psychology to healthcare and nursing? - 6 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. What is growth? - 5 marks
- b. How is development distinct from growth? - 2 marks
- c. Explain the three domains of development - 6 marks
- d. What is Down syndrome? - 2 marks
- e. Mention the three stages involved in prenatal development - 3 marks
- f. How does hereditary influence growth and development? - 2 marks

QUESTION THREE

- a. Define Psychology - 2 marks
- b. State four (4) factors that influences growth and development? - 4 marks
- c. Give four (4) theories of growth and development and the personalities behind them? - 4 marks
- d. Define the following terminologies;
- i. Defense mechanisms - 2 marks
- ii. Schema - 2 marks
- iii. Schemata - 2 marks
- e. Mention the three (3) aspects of behaviour? - 3 mark
- f. Mention the type of psychological field that studies the following;
- i. Relationship between a number and some coinciding observed events - 1 mark

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC-BEREKUM/ ST. MARY'S CAMPUS - DROBO
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION - MAY 2017
RGNI9/ RM 14 (PNM 121) PSYCHOLOGY IN NURSING-
TIME ALLOWED-1 ½ HRS
ESSAY

INSTRUCTIONS:

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- Each question carries 20 marks
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QUESTION ONE

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- d. Enumerate six (6) importance of psychology to healthcare and nursing? - 6 marks

QUESTION TWO

- a. What is growth? - 5 marks
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QUESTION THREE

- a. Define Psychology - 2 marks
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- f. Mention the type of psychological field that studies the following;
- i. Relationship between a number and some coinciding observed events - 1 mark

NMTC-BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION-MAY 2016
RGN 18 & RM RGN 028/ HMDW 017 PSYCHOLOGY IN NURSING

TIME ALLOWED: 2 HOURS
THEORY QUESTIONS

INSTRUCTIONS:

- Answer all questions.
- Each question must be answered in a separate answer booklet
- Each question carries 20 marks
- Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers

Note that any number of points provided beyond the **NUMBER SPECIFIED** for each question will not attract any marks

Question One

- a. In not more than 15 words explain psychology to a secondary school graduate? - 1½ marks
- b. Mention the **FIVE (5)** schools of psychology and the various personalities behind them? - 5 marks
- c. Explain the key concept in Piaget's theory of cognitive development of personality? - 10marks
- d. i. Define an ego defense mechanism? - 1½ marks
- ii. Mention any **TWO (2)** components or characteristics of personality? - 2 marks

Question Two

- a. State **ONE (1)** similarity between the following?
- i. Oral stage and id - 2 marks
- ii. Oral stage and trust versus mistrust - 2 marks
- b. State **THREE(3)** attributes of learning? - 3 marks
- c. Enumerate **SIX (6)** importance of psychology to healthcare and nursing? - 6 marks
- d. i. What is development? - 2marks
- ii. Mention any **FIVE (5)** methods that can be used to assess the personality of individuals? - 5 marks

QUESTION Three

- a. Mention the **FOUR (4)** theories of learning and the personalities behind them? - 4 marks
- b. Explain how a dog which has been conditioned to salivate to the sound of bell will have that behaviour extinct? - 6 marks
- c. Define personality? - 2 marks
- d. Give **FOUR (4)** examples of neurotransmitter and its effect on behaviour? - 8 marks

QUESTION Four

- a. Enumerate the **FOUR (4)** theories of growth and development and the various personalities behind them? 4 marks
- b. Topographically arrange the stages involve in the following growth and development theories;
- i. The Psychosexual theory - 2 marks
- ii. The Psychosocial theory - 4 marks
- c. List four (4) domains of development of an individual? - 4 marks
- d. Enumerate **FOUR (4)** characteristics of each of the following:
- i. The Ego Defense mechanism - 2 marks
- ii. The Id - 2 marks
- iii. The Superego - 2 marks

INDEX NUMBER.....
HFNMTC – BEREKUM/ST. MARY'S CAMPUS – DROB
END OF SEMESTER EXAMINATION – MAY 2018
RGN 20 AND RM 15 PNM 121 INTRODUCTION TO PSYCHOLOGY
TIME ALLOWED: 1/30 MINUTES
ESSAY

Instructions

- *Answer all questions.*
- *Each question must be answered in a separate booklet*
- *Each question carries 20marks*
- *Read the question carefully and provide only relevant answers*
- *Note that any number of points provided beyond the NUMBER SPECIFIED for each question will not attract any mark.*

Question One

- a. (i) Define psychology and state why Modern Psychology is a science. - 2 Marks
- b. (ii) List the three aspects of behaviour. - 3 Marks
- c. Enumerate **three** (3) examples of pseudopsychology and two examples of parapsychology. - 5 Marks
- d. Briefly define **five** (5) of the branches of psychology - 5 Marks
- e. State any **five** (5) importance of psychology to healthcare and nursing. - 5 Marks

Question Two

- a. (i) Differentiate between growth and development - 2 Marks
- b. (ii) Define Personality - 3 Marks
- c. Mention any **five** (5) factors that influence growth and development - 5 Marks
- d. State the **five** (5) stages of Sigmund Freud's psychosexual stages of development with their corresponding ages. - 5 Marks
- e. Briefly explain the following in relation to the cognitive development theory: - 5 Marks
- i. Schema
 - ii. Schemata
 - iii. Assimilation
 - iv. Accommodation
 - v. Equilibration

Question Three

- a. Mention the three types of sensory memory. - 3 Marks
- b. What is reinforcement in operant conditioning? - 2 Marks
- c. Calculate the Intelligent Quotient (IQ) of Kwame who has a Mental Age (MA) of 12 and a Chronological Age (CA) of 10. - 5 Marks
- d. Give the five main principles of classical conditioning. - 5 Marks
- e. List **five negatives** about the use of punishment. - 5 Marks